

New Directions in Pesticide Research, Development, Management, and Policy

1993

**New Directions in Pesticide Research,
Development, Management, and Policy**

November 1-3, 1993

Program and Presenters' Abstracts

**Virginia Water Resources
Research Center**

Virginia
 Tech
VIRGINIA POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE
AND STATE UNIVERSITY

**A publication of the Virginia Water Resources Research Center,
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Diana L. Weigmann, Interim Director**

**Additional copies of this publication may be obtained
while supplies last from Publications Services,
Virginia Water Resources Research Center,
617 N. Main St., Blacksburg, VA 24060-3397.**

**Virginia Tech is an Equal Opportunity/Affirmative Action employer.
For more information, contact the University's EO/AA Office.**

Special recognition goes to Judy Poff for word processing, designing, and editing the abstract publication and program; S. I. Parsons for editing the abstracts; and G. W. Wills for the cover design.

COLLECTED ABSTRACTS
of the
FOURTH NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON PESTICIDES

**NEW DIRECTIONS IN PESTICIDE RESEARCH,
DEVELOPMENT, MANAGEMENT, AND POLICY**

November 1-3, 1993

**Hyatt Richmond
Richmond, Virginia**

Sponsored by

**Virginia Water Resources Research Center
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University**

**SCHEDULE OF EVENTS
AND
TABLE OF CONTENTS**

7:30 am	Registration — Ballroom Foyer
8:30-9:00 am	Welcome — Ballroom A Mark Schaefer, Assistant Director for the Environment, Office of Science and Technology
9:00-9:45 am	Opening — Ballroom A Victor Kimm, Acting Assistant Administrator, Office of Prevention, Pesticides, and Toxic Substances, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
9:45-10:00 am	ADJOURN for Session Meetings

Session Meetings

November 1, 1993

Session A (I): 10:00 am - 12:05 pm
Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Marvin A. Lawson, Office of Pesticide Management, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Richmond, VA

Chesapeake Bay Program: Partnership for Basinwide Implementation of Innovative Pesticide Management Programs

W. Matuszeski 1

An Overview of Integrated Pest Management and Pesticide-Use Surveys
B. H. Marose 2

Meeting Pesticide Challenges in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed — Best Management Practices
M. E. Setting 3

Pesticide Disposal and Container Recycling in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed
D. D. Bingaman 5

Pesticide Management through Whole-Farm Planning	
N. D. Stone	7

Session B (I): 10:00 am - 12:05 pm
Monticello A/B

Moderator: Maureen G. Novotne, Director, Water Quality and Ecology Programs,
 Water Environment Federation, Alexandria, VA

PATRIOT — A Methodology and Decision Support System for Evaluating the Leaching Potential of Pesticides	
P. R. Hummel, J. C. Imhoff, J. L. Kittle, and R. F. Carsel	8

A Herbicide-Specific Soil Transport Sensitivity Analysis Utilizing Soil Surveys, Screening Models, PRZM, and a Geographic Information System	
R. T. Paulsen and K. Balu	9

Relation of Travel Time and Persistence to the Distribution of Pesticides and Nitrate in an Unconfined Aquifer in the New Jersey Coastal Plain	
Z. Szabo, D. E. Rice, T. Ivahnenko, and E. F. Vowinkel	11

Evaluation of Groundwater Vulnerability to Pesticides in the Thomas Jefferson Planning District, Virginia	
S. Shukla, S. Mostaghimi, V. O. Shanholtz, and M. C. Collins	13

A Summary of Government Agency Data on the Occurrence of Pesticides in Indiana Groundwater	
M. R. Risch	15

LUNCH: 12:05 - 1:45 pm
Ballroom A/B

Speaker: Michael Robinson, Director, National Zoo, Smithsonian Institute,
 Washington, DC; **Title:** *The Tropics as a Source of New Defenses Against Old Enemies*

Session A (II): 1:45 - 3:50 pm
Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Marvin A. Lawson, Office of Pesticide Management, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Richmond, VA

Pesticide Monitoring in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed

D. L. Murphy 17

Groundwater Protection Will Provide Improved Water Quality for the Chesapeake Bay

M. A. Lawson 19

The Role of Education in Managing Pesticides in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed

A. E. Brown 20

Managing Nonagricultural Pesticides in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed

S. A. Harrison 21

**Pesticides in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed: Challenges and Changes for the Future
Panel Discussion**

BREAK: 3:50 - 4:15 pm

Session B (II): 1:45 - 3:50 pm

Monticello A/B

Moderator: Khizar Wasti, Bureau of Toxic Substances, Virginia Department of Health, Richmond, VA

Drinking Water Compliance Problems from Pesticides and Herbicides

J. A. Roberson 22

Implementation of a Program to Assess the Vulnerability of New Jersey's Drinking Water Supplies to Pesticide Contamination

J. B. Louis, P. F. Sanders, and P. M. Bono 23

Method to Estimate the Vulnerability of New Jersey Drainage Basins Used for Public Supply to Contamination by Agricultural Pesticides

D. E. Buxton and D. A. Stedfast 24

Herbicides in Ohio's Drinking Water: Risk Assessment, Reductions, and Communication

D. B. Baker and R. P. Richards 25

Atrazine Exposures through Drinking Water: Three Midwestern Case Studies

R. P. Richards and D. B. Baker 26

BREAK: 3:50 - 4:15 pm

SESSION A (III): 4:15 - 5:30 pm

Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Brenda Sahli, member, Virginia Pesticide Control Board, Richmond, VA

Herbicides in Soil and Water at Three Kentucky Farm Sites

B. D. Jacobson and W. W. Witt 27

Alachlor Movement in a Coastal Plain Soil

W. F. Ritter, A. E. M. Chirnside, R. W. Scarborough, and G. Salthouse 28

Tillage Effects on Atrazine and Metolachlor Leaching in a Virginia Coastal Plain Soil

C. D. Heatwole, S. Zacharias, S. Mostaghimi, and T. A. Dillaha 30

SOCIAL: 5:45 - 7:45 pm — Ballroom A

Session B (III): 4:15 - 5:30 pm

Monticello A/B

Moderator: Allen James, Executive Director, Responsible Industry for a Sound Environment (RISE), Washington, DC

Evaluation of a Pilot Monitoring Project for 14 Pesticides in Maryland Surface Waters

R. Kroll, D. Murphy, and M. J. Garrels 31

Impact of Copper, Chromium, Arsenic, and Pentachlorophenol on Aquatic Macroinvertebrates in a North Georgia Forest Stream

M.A. Callahan, P. B. Bush, D. G. Neary, R. A. LaFayette, and J. W. Taylor, Jr. 33

Pilot Development of a Freshwater Molluscan Sediment BioAssay for Pesticides

H. L. Phelps 34

SOCIAL: 5:45 - 7:45 pm — Ballroom A

November 2, 1993

Session A (I): 8:30 - 10:10 am
Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Donald J. Lott, Chief, Pesticide Management Section, U.S. EPA, Region III, Philadelphia, PA

Pesticide Use Surveys in Arizona — What Do They Show?

P.B. Baker, S. Merrigan, D. Fairchild, B. Bloyd, and W. Sherman 35

Pesticide Use in Virginia: Results of the 1991 Statewide Surveys

F. E. Abdaoui and M. J. Weaver 36

A Nine-Year Comparison of Pesticide Use in New Jersey

G. C. Hamilton and R. Meyer 37

Assessing Pesticide Use in New Jersey by Means Other Than Amounts

C. R. Brown and L. W. Meyer 38

BREAK: 10:10 - 10:35 am

Session B (I): 8:30 - 10:10 am
Monticello A/B

Moderator: Bruce A. Julian, U.S.D.A. Soil Conservation Service, Richmond, VA

Automated Solid Phase Extraction for Pesticides and Herbicides in Large-Volume Water Samples

D. S. Williams 39

Monitoring Atrazine After Turf Application Using Immunoassays

A. M. Wowk, C. R. Brown, and R. W. Meyer 40

Extraction of Pesticides from Soil, Plant, and Water Samples by Classical and Supercritical Fluid Methods

R. G. Frazier and G. Winnett 41

Significant Improvements in Multiresidue Pesticide Analysis

J. D. Rosen, P. S. Mogadati, S. Wang, K. S. Roinestad, and I. Kambhampati . 42

BREAK: 10:10 - 10:35 am

Session A (II): 10:35 am - 12:15 pm
Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Patricia A. Woodson, Virginia Department of Environmental Quality,
Richmond, VA

**Concepts for a National Synthesis of Pesticides in Major River Basins and Aquifer
Systems**

W. G. Wilber and R. J. Gilliom 43

Canadian Water Quality Guidelines for Pesticides

P. Y. Caux and R. A. Kent 44

**The Challenge of Planning Ahead: A Case Study in the Development of Virginia's
Generic Pesticides and Groundwater Management Plan**

M. A. Lawson, A. B. Dotson, F. Dukes, M. K. Curtin, and D. J. Schweitzer . . 46

Agrichemical Groundwater Quality Protection in Idaho: Management and Policies

D. C. Whitney and L. L. Mink 47

Session B (II): 10:35 am - 12:15 pm
Monticello A/B

Moderator: John Johnson, Assistant Director of Public Affairs, Virginia Farm Bureau,
Richmond, VA

Pesticide Contamination of Targeted Household Water Supplies

B. B. Ross, T. Younos, T. A. Dillaha, R. W. Young, and N. M. Herbert 49

**Well Vulnerability and Nitrate Contamination: Assessments from a Voluntary Well
Testing Program**

D. B. Baker and R. P. Richards 51

**Evaluation of the Vulnerability of Water from Public Supply Wells in New Jersey to
Contamination by Pesticides by Use of a Geographic Information System**

E. F. Vowinkel, R. M. Clawges, and C. G. Uchrin 52

Pesticide Degradates in Groundwater: Implications of Available Studies for Regulatory Policy

M. R. Barrett 53

LUNCH: 12:15 - 1:30 pm
Ballroom A/B

Speaker: Joseph Muldoon, Associate Council, Committee on Agriculture, U.S. House of Representatives, Washington, DC

Session A (III): 1:30 - 3:10 pm
Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Nancy Malloy, National Center for Food and Agriculture Policy, Washington, DC

Induced Systemic Resistance — A Non-Pesticide Technology for Disease Control in Plants

J.A. Kuc 54

Development of Environmentally Safe Chemicals as Inducers of Disease Resistance in Crop Plants

N.E. Strobel and J.A. Kuc 55

Higher Plant Products as Natural Pesticides

A.K. Mishra, N. Kishore, and N. K. Dubey 57

The Insecticidal Activity of Floral and Root Extracts of *Tagetes minuta* and *Tagetes patula* (Marigolds, Family-Asteraceae) Against Mexican Bean Weevils, *Zabrotes subfasciatus* and Nontarget Organisms, Fish (*Gambusia affinis*) and a Beneficial Insect, the Pirate Bug, *Xylocoris flavipes*

S. Sriharan, A. Wright, P. Singh, F. V. Dunkel, D. C. Richards, W. Bertsch, and C. Wells 58

BREAK: 3:10 - 3:35 pm

Session B (III): 1:30 - 3:10 pm
Monticello A/B

Moderator: Linda Lyon, Division of Environmental Contaminants, Fish and Wildlife Service, Arlington, VA

Summary of CIBA/State Groundwater Monitoring Study for Atrazine and Its Major Degradation Products in the United States

K. Balu, M. Cheung, C. Rock, J. Case, R. Ross, P. Holden, C. Eiden, and P. Swidersky 59

General Discussion of the 1988 EPA Draft Guidance for Groundwater Monitoring Studies and Recommendations for Modification of the Small-Scale Prospective Design Based on Field Experience

I. W. Buttler, K. Balu, and P. W. Holden 60

Validation of Enhancements to the Pesticide Root Zone Model: Metabolites, Irrigation, and Vadose Zone Transport

J. M. Cheplick, W. M. Williams, K. Balu, and R. F. Carsel 61

Application of PRZM-2 to Predict the Fate and Transport of Forest Site Preparation Herbicides on Clear-cut Sites

A. K. Shahlaee, P. B. Bush, W. L. Nutter, J. W. Taylor, and Y. C. Berisford . . 62

BREAK: 3:10 - 3:35 pm

Session A (IV): 3:35 - 5:40 pm
Ballroom C/D

Moderator: Don Delorme, Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Service, Richmond, VA

Predicting the Safety of New Pesticide Registrations to Man and the Environment Using Artificial Intelligence and Computer Knowledge Base Techniques

T. C. McDowell 63

A Fate and Transport Model to Evaluate and Manage Agrochemical Runoff from Rice Paddies

W. M. Williams, J. M. Cheplick, R. Layton, and J. G. Arnold 64

Movement of the Pyrethroid Insecticide Bifenthrin in a Georgia Piedmont Pine Seed Orchard

P. C. deGolian, Y. C. Berisford, P. B. Bush, J. W. Taylor, and W.L. Nutter . . . 65

Control of Pesticide Movement with Stormflow Detention Ponds

D. G. Neary, P. B. Bush, W. L. Nutter, and J. W. Taylor, Jr. 66

Monitoring of Pesticides on Golf Courses in New Jersey L. W. Meyer and C. Brown	67
---	----

Session B (IV): 3:35 - 5:40 pm
Monticello A/B

Moderator: Betsy Stinson, Wildlife Health Program Manager, Virginia Department of Game and Inland Fisheries, Blacksburg, VA

The Potential Roles of Herbicide Resistant Crops in the United States L. P. Gianessi and C. A. Puffer	68
---	----

Cutinases as Natural Adjuvants for Increasing the Uptake of Agrichemicals H. C. Gerard, R. A. Moreau, S. F. Osman, W. F. Fett	69
---	----

Environmental Risk Reduction in the Cranberry Industry T. J. Bicki	70
--	----

Opportunities and Obstacles for Proper Application and Management of Pesticides H. E. Ozkan	71
---	----

A Comparison of the Pesticides Used in Conventional and IPM-Grown Eggplant G. C. Hamilton and J. Lashomb	72
--	----

November 3, 1993

Session A (I): 8:30 - 10:35 am
Ballroom A

Moderator: Charles Finley, Jr., Virginia Forestry Association, Richmond, VA

A Review of Surface-Water Monitoring for Atrazine in the Chesapeake Bay Watershed (1976-1991) D. P. Tierney, W. M. Williams, A. L. Hahn, P. Holden, and L. Newby	73
--	----

Groundwater Transport of Pesticides to Surface Waters and Estuaries on the Eastern Shore of Virginia A. M. Dietrich, D. L. Gallagher, D. Schicho, T. Hubbard, W. Reay, G. M. Simmons, M. C. Hayes, S. W. Jourdan, and T. L. Lawruk	74
--	----

Temporal and Geographic Distribution of Herbicides in Precipitation in the Midwest and Northeast United States, 1990-91

D. A. Goolsby, E. M. Thurman, M. L. Pomes, and W. A. Battaglin 76

Relations Between Agricultural Chemical Use and Annual Transport of Agricultural Chemicals in Midwestern Rivers, 1991-92

W. A. Battaglin and D. A. Goolsby 78

A Review of Historical Surface-Water Monitoring for Atrazine in the Mississippi, Missouri, and Ohio Rivers, 1975-1991

D. P. Tierney, B. R. Christensen, and L. Newby 79

BREAK: 10:35 - 11:00 am

Session B (I): 8:30 - 10:35 am

Ballroom B

Moderator: Jack Waters, former Chair, AWWA, Virginia Section, Chesterfield County Utilities, Chesterfield, VA

Survey of Acaricide Use in Georgia's Managed Honey Bee Colonies

K. S. Delaplane 81

Scotchgard® Effects on Pesticide Removal from Farmers' Work Clothing During Laundering

S. L. Prior, D. A. M. Sterling, and G. H. Frazer 82

Development of Oxidative Stress and Induction of Oxidative Stress-Related Genes and Proteins in Lung, Heart, Liver, Kidney, Intestine, and Brain following Intratracheal Administration of Polyhalogenated Cyclic Hydrocarbons

G. Mukherjee, N. Maulik, M. Bagchi, D. Bagchi, S. Stohs, and D. K. Das 83

Human Health Risk Assessment from Chemically Contaminated Fish and Shellfish: A National and State Perspective

S. M. GhiasUddin 84

Methodology for an Integrated Evaluation of All Scientific Evidence Relating to the Safety of the Herbicide 2,4-D

K. G. Sund, G. L. Carlo, and I. C. Munro 85

BREAK: 10:35 - 11:00 am

Session A (II): 11:00 am - 1:05 pm
Ballroom A

Moderator: Harry H. Gregori, Jr., Director, Policy and Planning and Public Affairs,
Department of Environmental Quality, Richmond, VA

**Remediation of Alachlor-Impacted Soil Using the White Rot Fungus *P. chrysosporium*
in a Solar Heated Bioreactor**

M. J. McFarland, E. Baiden, and D. Wray 86

Biodegradation of Alachlor and Atrazine in Soil as a Function of Concentration

J. Gan, W. C. Koskinen, R. L. Becker, D. D. Buhler, and L. J. Jarvis 87

Containment Spray Systems for Apples

H. W. Hogmire, K. C. Elliott, and A. R. Collins 88

Ropes and Bands for Pest Control

I. Azmanov 89

Pesticide Litigation

L. L. Geyer 91

Session B (II): 11:00 am - 1:05 pm
Ballroom B

Moderator: Joel Artman, Department of Forestry, Charlottesville, VA

Importance of Pesticide Science in University IPM Curricula

J. All 92

Vegetation Management with Environmental Stewardship

R. A. Johnstone 93

BayScapes Project

B. W. Mills 94

The Problem of Pesticides	
R. Williams	95
Frequency of Chromosomal Aberrations of Ascorbic Acid on Dimethoate in Human Lymphocyte Cultures	
D. Geetanjali and P. P. Reddy	97
Regulating Pesticide Use in Developing Countries: Problems and Suggestions	
S. C. Saxena	98

Atrazine Exposures through Drinking Water: Three Midwestern Case Studies

R. P. Richards¹ and D. B. Baker¹

Drinking water exposure assessments for a large population involve dividing the population into segments for which both the water source and the exposure concentration can be expected to be the same, and then determining the population and the exposure concentration for as many of these segments as possible. A population segment might be as small as those people served by an individual water treatment plant, or as broad as those people who use private wells as a water source. The segmentation is usually dictated by the availability of data on which to base an estimate of the exposure concentration, which should be a reasonable estimate of the long-term average concentration to which an individual is exposed. Often, data result from worst-case sampling programs and are unevenly spaced in time; in these cases, a time-weighted average must be used to avoid a biased exposure concentration.

The assessment is conveniently displayed as an exposure concentration exceedency plot, which represents the population segments by rectangles, with width proportional to the population and height proportional to the exposure concentration, arranged in order of decreasing concentration, and color-coded to represent the source of the drinking water. We have developed a Macintosh computer program that converts a data table into such a display.

An exposure assessment for a large area such as a state is bound to require the use of some population segments for which the data is fairly good, some for which it is poor, and some for which it is non-existent. The data gap for the last group can be handled by extrapolation from other related population segments, by modeling, by best professional judgement, or in several other ways. One of the advantages of doing a large-area population assessment is that it identifies the parts of the population that are inadequately characterized. As better data become available, the assessment can be updated and improved.

Assessments have been done for the states of Ohio and Illinois, and for the populations that draw their drinking water from the Ohio-Missouri-Mississippi river system. An assessment of the state of Iowa is underway. Even though worst-case assumptions were made to resolve any points of uncertainty, none of these assessments identified any substantial population blocks that are exposed to atrazine through drinking water at concentrations that exceed the MCL of 3.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$. In general, groundwater and the Great Lakes are the sources with lowest atrazine concentrations, while rivers draining agricultural watersheds and some reservoirs on these rivers have the highest concentrations.

¹Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College, 310 E. Market St., Tiffin, OH 44883